

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

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How to cite this paper:

Garcia, E. and Simbulan, S. (2021). Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College. *School of Education Research Journal*, 2(1), 45-61. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17027.02089>

Received: October 21, 2021
Accepted: October 23, 2021
Published: November 22, 2021

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ABSTRACT

The linchpin of this study is on the stakeholders' evaluation of the SED curriculum of AY 2020-2021. Seven stakeholders purposively selected from the faculty, alumni, students, employers, and industry practitioners' sectors participated in the evaluation of the curriculum as to their relevance to the program, connectivity of the subjects from first to fourth year, and the adequacy of the curriculum to prepare the prospective graduates for their future career. Findings revealed that the stakeholders strongly agreed that the BEED and BSED curricular programs are relevant. The subjects offered are connected from first to fourth year. The courses are adequate to prepare the graduates for their future teaching career. There were comments and suggestions given by the stakeholders especially on some subjects that seem disconnected, subjects that need proper sequencing especially the prerequisite subjects, and renaming of some subjects. In a nutshell, the involvement and participation of the stakeholders have proven that the evaluation of the curriculum is a vital academic exercise.

Subject Area

Curriculum Evaluation

Keywords: *Stakeholders, Evaluation, School of Education Curriculum*

INTRODUCTION

Former USA's First Lady Hilary Clinton said, "*it takes the whole village to educate a child*" (Dela Cruz, 2015). This famous adage comes from an old African proverb "*It takes a village to raise a child*" (O'Keefe, 2011) indicating that the school is a conglomeration of stakeholders that involve the faculty, alumni, parents, employers, and industry practitioners, who contribute to have

a better education of the students. The involvement of stakeholders in the evaluation of the curriculum encompasses a whole gamut of a child's academic growth and development.

Evaluation of curriculum is an essential and vital part of the whole process of curriculum development. It is a continuous activity done by people in the academe with the stakeholders' involvement. The importance of curriculum evaluation is to determine the value of the curriculum itself as to whether it is relevant, appropriate, and significant for the particular group of students with whom it is being used. Curriculum evaluation aims to examine the impact of implemented curriculum on student (learning) achievement so that the official curriculum can be revised if necessary and to review teaching and learning processes in the classroom (SA, 2021; IPL, 2020).

An evaluation of the teacher education curriculum shows a need to have more courses in the major field. For practical reasons, teachers need more depth and breadth in their field of specialization. An uninformed or ignorant teacher can do much harm. A program of carefully chosen courses in content is imperative for teachers to develop a solid grasp of the goals and objectives of a field. Overall academic performance is positively associated with successful teaching. It must be emphasized, however, that good teaching does not automatically occur when teachers know their subject. While research suggests that knowledge of subject matter does not necessarily make a person a good teacher of that subject, it seems reasonable to conclude that teachers with good instructional capabilities would be more effective if they had in-depth knowledge of the subjects they teach (Savellano, 1999).

The relevance of the curriculum could be evaluated through curriculum research. Curriculum research gives the evidence how much curriculum programs and educational institutions work out at the level satisfactory for society, policy makers, teacher staff, students and their parents. Continual evaluation of realization of educational processes is the condition for the success of any educational reform. Apart from the assessment of progress toward goals, includes study of questions where one program is good for (Maksic, 2018). The question on whether the program is better than other and how can it be improved are generally asked. Current school curriculum has to respond to dramatic social changes, growth of an information-oriented society, the development of science and technology, and the quest for quality assurance, and the adaption to the changing cultural milieu of the time.

The stakeholders' evaluation of the curriculum is relevant for quality assurance. The courses offered, the sequencing of subjects, the prerequisite subjects required, the number of units per semester, the appropriate level for offering the subjects, the total number of units required to finish a course, and other essential considerations are some aspects that need to be assessed. There are instances when students and parents would find the curriculum too loaded, not only because of the schedules of the students but also on the financial burden these subjects would entail for the parents. These usually are felt by the students during mid-term and final examinations when they have too many subjects to study; and the parents worrying as to how they will be able to pay their children's tuition.

Generally, San Isidro College follows the CHED-approved curricula for the School of Education (SED). However, there are accrediting bodies like the Philippine Accrediting Association for Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU) who would promulgate quality assurance requiring schools to involve stakeholders in the evaluation of the curriculum. This

academic exercise is relevant for PAASCU to ensure monitoring and evaluation of the curriculum offered by the school, as to whether the subjects offered are appropriate or adequate for the graduates of a particular course.

This study therefore sought to investigate the stakeholders' involvement in the curriculum evaluation of the SED programs for them to be aware of the relevance, adequateness, connectivity of the subjects, and appropriateness of the courses taken by the students that would prepare them for their future career.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Curriculum evaluation processes adhere to the idea that curriculum contents, teaching and methods of instruction have to be adapted to the developmental capacities of students. The turning point in curriculum evaluation is Vygotsky's idea of the leading role of learning where teaching is internally necessary and universal moment of a student's development. Curriculum contents and learning are more valuable if they are not only active to fulfill learner's mental schemes but proactive and provoking the individual's development (Maksic, 2018).

Institutional stakeholders play a very important role during development and implementation of curriculum. At present, the public get closely involved on the activities of learning institutions upon realizing that they affect their lives because of the programs they offer. Stakeholders are increasingly questioning the economic impact of some of the learning activities carried out by universities. This therefore implies that concerned parties in the operations of institutions are demanding the opportunity to influence the decisions made by them (Buckens & Hinton, 1998). It is therefore important for any university/college to engage its stakeholders from curriculum formulation to its implementation through needs assessment.

Stakeholder theory was first described by Dr. F. Edward Freeman in 1984. It suggests that shareholders are merely one of many stakeholders in a company/institution. A commonly used definition is of Freeman who stated that stakeholders are any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization's objectives (Chepkemoi & Juma., 2019). Stakeholders influence or are influenced by an institution, either they depend on institution or institutions are dependent on them. Institutions need stakeholders to make profit, to develop programs and to continue to exist. In turn, stakeholders need institutions for employment and wealth. There is a mutual dependency and that is why it is crucial that the relationship between institutions and stakeholders is well maintained (Friedman & Miles, 2006; Manetti, 2011; Porter & Kramer, 2006). Stakeholder theory has been applied to investigate the role of stakeholders in higher education (Amaral & Magalhaes, 2002; Jongbloed et al., 2008). Stakeholder theory confirms the idea that stakeholders influence the quality and sustainability of the curriculum hence institutions need to take into consideration the different opinions and expectations of the stakeholders. Stakeholders are —those groups who are crucial to the survival and success of the institution (Freeman, R. E., Harrison, J. S., Wicks, A. C., Parmar, B. L., & De Colle, S., 2010). It can be said that stakeholders could be the makers or breakers of an institution, as they put pressure on institutions and could have a significant influence on the outcome.

Stakeholders are individuals or institutions that are interested in the school curriculum. Their interests vary in degree and complexity. They get involved in many ways in the implementation,

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

because the curriculum affects them directly or indirectly. These stakeholders shape the school curriculum implementation (Durgaryan, 2020).

At San Isidro College, the stakeholders include the faculty, students, alumni, employers, and industry practitioners. In this particular study, the stakeholders evaluated the curriculum for the SED as to courses' relevance, the sequencing of subjects offered, the connectivity of the subjects, and their adequacy as to prepare the students for their future career. The School of Education has the following programs: Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEE) and the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE) majors in English, Filipino, Mathematics and Values Education. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 1. The schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study investigated the stakeholders' evaluation of the curriculum for both the School of Education for quality assurance.

It sought to answer the following:

1. What is the stakeholders' evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum for the following:
 - 1.1 Bachelor of Elementary Education; and
 - 1.2 Bachelor of Secondary Education, majors in Mathematics, Filipino, English and Values Education?
2. What are the comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the SED curriculum in:
 - 2.1 Bachelor of Elementary Education; and
 - 2.2 Bachelor of Secondary Education, majors in English, Filipino, Mathematics and Values Education?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design employing quantitative and qualitative analysis based from the result of the evaluation of School of Education (SED) stakeholders which include the faculty, alumni, students, employers and industry practitioners. San Isidro College served as the research locale of the study where the stakeholders are invited to attend a meeting for the evaluation of the curriculum.

San Isidro College is the only Catholic the Institution of Higher learning located in Impalambong Malaybalay City. It was founded by Jesuit Missionaries in July 1949 and is duly accredited by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd). It is also a member of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP) and the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS). Its motto *Ora et Labora* which means *prayer and work* is the famous flagship of San Isidro Labrador, the patron saint of Malaybalay City. From its humble beginnings, the school continues to provide quality Catholic Education where students adhere to its philosophy, vision, mission, core values and graduate attributes.

There is a total of seven respondents who were purposively selected to represent the faculty, alumni, students, employers and the practitioners' group. This was especially deliberated due to the COVID pandemic and limited number of respondents to represent the sector they belong. The data were from the SIC prepared questionnaire that would evaluate the stakeholders' opinion on the relevance of the course, the connectivity of the subjects offered, and the adequacy of the curriculum to prepare the graduates for their future career. The SED respondents were provided the courses offered for the SED in all the programs. The respondents were represented by the faculty, alumni, students, employers, and industrial practitioners. All the respondents received the curricular offerings and the evaluation instrument. The facilitators during the forum collected the responses of the stakeholders after they have responded to the evaluation instrument, these were then tallied, tabulated and analyzed to answer the problems set in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Stakeholders' Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum

Getting employed after graduation is often a motivation of the students to pursue their course. More and more college degree become a pre-requisite for employment. Hence, the need to look into the curriculum and see what makes the graduate of teacher education acquire work immediately after graduation. The stakeholders could serve as good evaluators of the curriculum especially because their children are the beneficiaries of the good education.

Table 1 illustrates the stakeholders' evaluation of the freshmen curriculum. From the Table the stakeholders *strongly agreed* on the relevance, proper sequencing/ordering of the subjects and adequacy of the freshmen curriculum for the BEED. They *strongly agreed* that the curriculum could prepare the BEED students for their future teaching career. This means that the provisions in the freshmen curriculum were very adequately satisfied. The indicator showing the highest mean is on the adequacy of the subjects offered that could help the students in their future career.

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

Table 1. The schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study.

School of Education Curriculum FIRST YEAR - First and Second Semester	BEEd	BSEd English	BSEd Filipino	BSEd Math	BSEd ValEd	TOTAL	QD
1. The subjects for the FIRST year, first semester is relevant for the field of specialization	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.83	4.93	Strongly Agree
2. The subjects for the FIRST year, second semester are relevant for the field of specialization	4.83	4.83	4.83	5.00	5.00	4.89	Strongly Agree
3. There is proper/orderly sequencing of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.67	4.50	4.67	4.83	4.83	4.76	Strongly Agree
4. There is connectivity of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.67	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.79	Strongly Agree
5. The subjects will prepare the students for their future career	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.96	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.89	4.89	4.85	Strongly Agree

Similarly, the stakeholders *strongly agreed* that the sophomore BEED curriculum is relevant as illustrated in Table 2. The subjects are properly sequenced and well connected. They *strongly agreed* that the sophomore curriculum could prepare the student for their teaching career. This indicates that the provisions in the sophomore curriculum were very adequately satisfied.

Table 2. Stakeholders' Evaluation of the School of Education for the Sophomore Curriculum.

School of Education Curriculum SECOND YEAR - First and Second Semester	BEEd	BSEd English	BSEd Filipino	BSEd Math	BSEd ValEd	TOTAL	QD
1. The subjects for the SECOND year, first semester is relevant for the field of specialization	4.67	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.90	Strongly Agree
2. The subjects for the SECOND year, second semester are relevant for the field of specialization	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.50	4.83	4.83	Strongly Agree
3. There is proper/orderly sequencing of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.33	4.50	4.67	4.83	4.33	4.53	Strongly Agree
4. There is connectivity of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.50	4.50	4.83	4.50	4.67	4.60	Strongly Agree
5. The subjects will prepare the students for their future career	4.83	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.93	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.67	4.76	4.90	4.69	4.76	4.76	Strongly Agree

Likewise, as shown in Table 3, the stakeholders *strongly agreed* that the junior BEED curriculum is relevant. The subjects are properly sequenced as well as there is connectivity from first to second semester. The subjects are adequate and could prepare the students for their future teaching career.

Table 3. Stakeholders' Evaluation of the School of Education for the Junior Curriculum.

School of Education Curriculum THIRD YEAR - First and Second Semester	BEEEd	BSEd English	BSEd Filipino	BSEd Math	BSEd ValEd	TOTAL	QD
1. The subjects for the THIRD year, first semester is relevant for the field of specialization	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.83	4.83	4.89	Strongly Agree
2. The subjects for the THIRD year, second semester are relevant for the field of specialization	5.00	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.86	Strongly Agree
3. There is proper/orderly sequencing of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.67	4.83	4.16	4.50	4.33	4.49	Strongly Agree
4. There is connectivity of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.83	4.67	4.50	4.50	4.67	4.63	Strongly Agree
5. The subjects will prepare the students for their future career	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.97	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.90	4.83	4.69	4.69	4.73	4.77	Strongly Agree

Table 4 presents the stakeholders' evaluation of the fourth-year curriculum. It is in this year level where the stakeholders rated very high in their agreement as to the relevance of the curriculum, the proper sequencing of the subjects; the connectivity of the subjects in the first and second semester; and the adequacy of the subjects to prepare the students for their teaching career. The stakeholders *strongly agreed* to all the provisions of the curriculum.

Table 4. Stakeholders' Evaluation of the School of Education for the Senior Curriculum.

School of Education Curriculum THIRD YEAR - First and Second Semester	BEEEd	BSEd English	BSEd Filipino	BSEd Math	BSEd ValEd	TOTAL	QD
1. The subjects for the THIRD year, first semester is relevant for the field of specialization	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.83	4.83	4.89	Strongly Agree
2. The subjects for the THIRD year, second semester are relevant for the field of specialization	5.00	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.86	Strongly Agree
3. There is proper/orderly sequencing of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.67	4.83	4.16	4.50	4.33	4.49	Strongly Agree
4. There is connectivity of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.83	4.67	4.50	4.50	4.67	4.63	Strongly Agree
5. The subjects will prepare the students for their future career	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	4.97	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.90	4.83	4.69	4.69	4.73	4.77	Strongly Agree

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

The summary assessment in Table 5 illustrates that the stakeholders *strongly agreed* on the relevance of the curriculum in all year levels for both the first and second semesters. They *strongly agreed* that there is proper/orderly sequencing of the subjects for the first and second semester. They also *strongly agreed* that there is connectivity of the subjects from the first to the second semester. Finally, they *strongly agreed* that the curriculum from first to fourth year will prepare the student for their future career as a teacher. It is in the senior year where the stakeholders gave a perfect rating in all the indicators. This could be because of the internship of the students happens during this year level. Students' actual class observation and practice teaching are done. The student internship is the highlight of the course.

Table 5. Summary on the Stakeholders' Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculums.

School of Education Curriculum	1 st Year	2 nd Year	3 rd Year	4 th Year	Total	QD
1. The subjects of the programs in the first semester are relevant for the field of specialization	4.93	4.90	4.89	5.00	4.93	Strongly Agree
2. The subjects of the programs in the second semester are relevant for the field of specialization	4.89	4.83	4.86	5.00	4.89	Strongly Agree
3. There is proper/orderly sequencing of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.76	4.53	4.49	5.00	4.65	Strongly Agree
4. There is connectivity of the subjects for the first and second semester	4.79	4.60	4.63	5.00	4.75	Strongly Agree
5. The subjects will prepare the students for their future career	4.96	4.93	4.97	5.00	4.96	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.85	4.76	4.77	5.00	4.845	Strongly Agree

As mentioned by Glenn (2018) an effective and relevant curriculum provides teachers, students, administrators and community stakeholders with a measurable plan and structure for delivering a quality education. The curriculum identifies the learning outcomes, standards and core competencies that students must demonstrate before advancing to the next level. Teachers play a key role in developing, implementing, assessing and modifying the curriculum. An evidenced-based curriculum acts as a road map for teachers and students to follow on the path to academic success.

Wells (2013) mentioned that a curriculum outlines for students a sequence of courses and tasks that must be successfully completed to master a subject and earn a diploma or degree. Students may be more motivated to study if they understand why certain subjects are taught in the curriculum. A curriculum reassures students that they're on the right track to reaching their goals and honing desired skills. All learning should make use of the natural connections that exist between learning areas and that link learning areas to the values and key competencies (Wells, 2013). A curriculum prepares an individual with the knowledge to be successful, confident and responsible citizens (Lounge,2020).

A connected curriculum promotes interdisciplinary questions and challenges, encouraging both staff and students to critically question the nature of evidence and knowledge production across different subject fields especially in a digitally-mediated world (UCL, 2017). It would seem to show that the BEED curriculum is a subject-centered one, spiraling around the subjects to be taught. It aims to expose students to a wide variety of ideas over and over again. A spiral curriculum, by moving in a circular pattern from topic to topic, aims to catch students when they first become ready to comprehend a concept. At the same time, a spiral curriculum works to continuously reinforce the fundamentals of this concept, to ingrain these fundamentals in the students' knowledge base, and to prevent losing students who aren't ready for the new lesson (Edupedia,2018).

Comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BEED Curriculum

The SED - BEED curriculum follows the prescribed curriculum of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). This usually includes the general education curriculum, the professional courses, the major subjects, the electives and the additional courses inherent at San Isidro College.

Matrix 1 shows the comments and suggestions of the stakeholders in their evaluation of the BEED curriculum. As noted, the stakeholder commented on the sequencing of some subjects. A faculty stakeholder stated that EEL 101 (*Teaching Multigrade Classes*) which is offered in the 2nd semester of the first year could be taken in the 3rd year since the students are now ready to practice the theories and concepts, they have learned in the first and second years. Besides in the third year, the subjects included are mostly on teaching the different subjects in the different areas like teaching English, Mathematics, Science, Filipino, Social Studies and Technology for both the first and second semesters

Matrix 1. Comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BEED Curriculum.

Comments of the stakeholders on the BEED Curriculum	Suggestions of the Stakeholders for the improvement of the BEED Curriculum
BEED-1	BEED-1
F- EEL 101 can be taken in 3 rd year F- These are all the basics and are primarily relevant to the first-year students A-The additional subjects on IGP and Theology will prepare the students not only on their career but also to the real world S- There are some subjects that is not appropriate or in line with the curriculum	IP- Theo 101 be offered in the first semester
BEED-2	BEED-2
F - GEC 108 & Fil 100 can be taken in 2 nd year F - The subjects are aligned with each other but the discontinuity of Ed Tech 1 in the 2 nd year and Ed Tech 2 in the 3 rd year may cause lagging or stagnation in the subjects learning (Technology for teaching and learning) S - The subjects in the first semesters are not connected to some subjects in the second year	F- Ed Tech 1 should be offered in the 2 nd semester so continuity of Ed Tech 1 and 2 could progress. A- Interchange EED 106 and EED 114 so that the EED 119 will be offered together with the PE 104 S- Theo 102 should be in the first year, 1 st sem. because it is a minor subject and it fits with other subjects IP- Theo 102 should be Christology not Marriage and Family Life

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

BEED-3	BEED-3
F- The Ed Tech 2 discontinuity and the Fil subject (Technology for teaching and learning)	F- The Fil 100 subject may be offered earlier (in 1 st /2 nd year) so students may focus on the major subjects and core subjects. Ed Tech 1 should be offered in the 2 nd sem of 2 nd year. S- The subjects are properly arranged
BEED-4	BEED-4
No comments	S- Why is there a need for research subject when it is tackled back in the 3 rd year

Legend: F – Faculty A – Alumni S – Student E – Employer IP – Industry Practitioner

The GEC 108 (*Science Technology and Society*) and Fil 100 (*Malikhain kasanayan sa Komposisyon at Pagsulat sa Filipino*) which are offered in the 1st and 2nd semester of the third year could be offered in the second year instead. This could allow the students to concentrate on the subjects that they will be teaching or practicing and their major field of concentration.

ED 106 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning I*) offered in the 1st semester of 2nd year is not immediately followed by EED 112 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning II*) because this is offered in the 1st semester of the 3rd year. There is a gap of one semester prior to its offering; hence there is a discontinuity of the knowledge and skills involved.

There are additional subjects distinct for San Isidro College and these include the IGP (*Isidran Guidance Program*) and Theology subjects which are inherent in Catholic schools. Accordingly, one stakeholder mentioned that these added subjects not only hone the students in their professional career but also prepare them for life in the real world. The core values of Christian education will make the Isidran graduate distinctly unique from the other college graduates in Malaybalay City.

The practitioner stakeholder commented that Theo 101 should be placed in the 1st semester of the first year and that Theo 102 should be on *Christology* and not on *Marriage and Family Life*. This suggestion was well taken but the making of this course was based on how the signs of the times affect the lives of the students in today's generation.

Matrix 2 shows the comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on their evaluation of the BSED English curriculum. A faculty stakeholder stated that Eng Ed 110 (*Principles & theories of Language*) could be taken in the second year, while Eng Ed 106 (*Mythology and Folklore*) which is offered in the 1st semester of the 2nd year could be in the 1st semester of the 3rd year.

The same comment on the discontinuity of the ED 106 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning I*) offered in the 1st semester of 2nd year is not immediately followed by Eng Ed 112 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning II*) because this is offered in the 1st semester of the 3rd year. There is a gap of one semester prior to its offering; hence there is a discontinuity of the knowledge and skills involved.

One stakeholder noted that the BSED English curriculum is loaded with more number of units, however she commended on this because this will hone the students to develop time management skills which they will need later as they practice their future career. It is noted that the BSED curriculum are loaded because the CHED no longer allowed the offering of summer classes, unless it is urgently needed and that CHED has permitted the school to offer.

The practitioner stakeholder still commented that Theology 1 be offered in the 1st semester of the first year and that Theo 102 should be on *Christology* and not on *Marriage and Family Life*. To have this in place Eng Ed 102 will be swapped with Theo 101 in its offering.

Matrix 2. Comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BSEd-English Curriculum

Comments of the stakeholders on the BSED-ENGLISH Curriculum	Suggestions of the Stakeholders for the improvement of the BSED-ENGLISH Curriculum
BSED-ENGLISH 1	BSED-ENGLISH 1
F-These are the foundation subjects and are the ones that establish understanding for the higher subjects A-The additional loads due to No Summer classes will teach the students on time management which is a skill they should master P- There is no Theology in the 1 st semester	A- I suggest to offer Eng Ed 101 in 3 rd yr, 1 st sem; Eng Ed 111 in 3 rd yr 2 nd sem; Eng Ed 108 in 1sy tr, 1 st sem P- Theo 101 be offered the 1 st semester; EngEd 102 be offered the 2 nd sem
BSED-ENGLISH 2	BSED-ENGLISH 2
F- Eng Ed 106 be taken in 3 rd yr, 1 st sem; F- The discontinuity of Ed Tech I and Ed Tech II stagnates the learning of the students in the said subjects S- Gender and Society is not related to the said major	F- Offer Ed Tech I in the 2 nd sem of the 2 nd yr
BSED-ENGLISH 3	BSED-ENGLISH 3
F- Eng Ed 110 can be taken in the 2 nd year F- The discontinuity of Ed Tech I and Ed Tech II S- Filipino is not connected to the field of specialization	F- The subject Ed Tech 1 maybe offered during the 2 nd sem of the 2 nd yr
BSED-ENGLISH 4	BSED-ENGLISH 4
No comments	
Legend: F – Faculty A – Alumni S – Student E – Employer IP – Industry Practitioner	

Matrix 3 shows the comments and suggestions of the stakeholders in their evaluation of the BSED-Filipino curriculum. A faculty stakeholder commented that Fil Ed 104 (*Estruktura ng Wikang Filipino*) could be taken in the 3rd year during the 1st semester. She added that Fil Ed 105 (*Pagtuturo at Pagtatanya Makrong Kasanayang Pangwika*) could be offered in the 3rd year during the 1st semester., since this is already on teaching. Fil 108 (*Paghahanda at Ebalkwasyon ng Kagamitang Panturo*) could be taken in 3rd year during the 1st semester since it should go with the teaching of content subjects. Fil Ed 106 (*Ugnayan ng Wika, Kultura at Lipunan*) could be taken in the 2nd year during the 1st semester since it should go with the teaching of content subjects.

Similarly, the comment on the discontinuity in the offering of ED 106 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning I*) offered in the 1st semester of 2nd year is not immediately followed by Fil Ed 112 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning II*) because this is offered in the 1st semester of the 3rd year. There is a gap of one semester prior to its offering; hence there is a discontinuity of the knowledge and skills involved.

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

Still the practitioner stakeholder commented on the offering of Theology 101 to be in the first semester of the first year and that Theology 2 should be on *Christology* and not on *Marriage and Family Life*.

Matrix 3. Comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BSEd-Filipino Curriculum

Comments of the stakeholders on the BSED-FILIPINO Curriculum	Suggestions of the Stakeholders for the improvement of the BSED-FILIPINO Curriculum
BSED- FILIPINO 1	BSED- FILIPINO 1
F- Fil Ed 104 can be taken 3 rd yr 1 st sem F- The subjects are the foundation subjects which are the basis for higher subjects later on	A- Interchange Fil Ed Fil Ed 102 & Fil Ed 104 P- Theo 101 be offered 1 st semester
BSED- FILIPINO 2	BSED- FILIPINO 2
F- Fil Ed 105 can be taken 3 rd yr 1 st sem., since it's on teaching already; Fil 108 can be taken 3 rd yr 1 st sem since it should go with the teaching of content; Fil Ed 106 can be taken 2 nd yr 1 st sem since it should go with the teaching of content F- The discontinuity of Ed Tech I and Ed Tech II in the higher year will cut the students' learning of the said subject S- Sacramental Theology is not related	F- Fil Ed 106 can be taken 1 st year, second sem since it can be part of the Introduction to language F- Offer Ed Tech I in the 2 nd semester
BSED- FILIPINO 3	BSED- FILIPINO 3
F- The discontinuity of Ed Tech I and II in the 2 nd and 3 rd yr; and Fil 100 in the higher year	F- Offer Ed Tech 1 in the 2 nd sem of the 2 nd yr.; Offer Filipino 100 in the earlier year so learners may focus on the major and core subjects more efficiently
BSED- FILIPINO 4	BSED- FILIPINO 4
No comments	
Legend: F – Faculty A – Alumni S – Student E – Employer IP – Industry Practitioner	

Matrix 4 shows the comments and suggestions of the stakeholders' evaluation of the BSED-Mathematics curriculum. A faculty stakeholder considered the freshmen curriculum as the basic foundation subjects for Mathematics. However, he commented that Math 104 (*Logic and Set Theory*) be offered in the 2nd semester of the first year to be swapped with Math Ed 101 (*History of Mathematics*) which is offered in the 1st semester of the first year. This is because Math Ed 104 lay the foundation for many math subjects in the higher years, and that Math 101 could be offered anytime.

The subject ED 106 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning I*) offered in the 1st semester of 2nd year needs to be followed by Math Ed 112 (*Technology for Teaching and Learning II*) because this is offered in the 1st semester of the 3rd year. There is a gap of one semester prior to its offering; hence there is a discontinuity of the knowledge and skills involved. This one semester gap may cause some lag in the learning of Technology by the students.

Advanced Statistics (Math 108) needs to be taught with Calculus II as it uses integrals which is not covered in Calculus I. Math Ed 112 which is on Technology in Math is taught in the 3rd year during the first semester which is also needed for computer software for advanced algebra.

He then suggested that ED 106 be offered in the 2nd semester of the 2nd year to have continuity of Technology I and II

The alumni stakeholder considered the Mathematics curriculum as relevant and adequate such that she thinks this could prepare the student in their future career.

Matrix 4. Comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BSEd-Mathematics Curriculum

Comments of the stakeholders on the BSED- MATHEMATICS Curriculum	Suggestions of the Stakeholders for the improvement of the BSED- MATHEMATICS Curriculum
BSED- MATHEMATICS 1	BSED- MATHEMATICS 1
<p>F- The major subjects are the basic foundations of math. Logic and Set Theory may have been offered in the 1st semester because History of math could be offered anytime</p> <p>A- Indeed, a Math teacher in the future will take up an amazing curriculum just like this will surely become an effective and well minded teacher</p> <p>S- Some subjects are not in line with the field of specialization</p> <p>IP- Theology 101 should be offered in the 1st semester</p>	<p>F- Logic and Set Theory be swapped with History of math, as Logic and Set Theory lay the foundation for many subjects in the higher years.</p> <p>IP- Theo 101 be swapped with another subject such that it will be offered in the first semester</p>
BSED- MATHEMATICS 2	BSED- MATHEMATICS 2
<p>F- The subject for Technology for Teaching and Learning I need to be followed by Technology for Teaching and Learning II. A discontinuity of the subjects may lead to a stunting knowledge in the subject. Advanced Statistic need to be taught together or after Calculus II as it uses integrals which is not covered in Calculus I. Technology in Math is taught in 3rd year which is also needed for computer software for advanced algebra</p>	<p>F- Offer Technology for Teaching and Learning I in the 2nd semester to follow through with the 2nd part of the subject. Offer Advanced Statistic together or after Calculus II and Technology for Teaching and Learning II.</p> <p>IP- Theology 102 should be Christology and not Marriage and Family life</p>
BSED- MATHEMATICS 3	BSED- MATHEMATICS 3
<p>F- Abstract algebra should be offered after Linear algebra. Number Theory should be offered earlier as concepts in this subject are needed for other fields in math. Fil 100 should be offered in the earlier part of the program preferably in the first year.</p> <p>A- This will surely prepare the students in the future career with bonuses on IGP and Theology which will prepare them for the real world.</p> <p>S- Filipino is not suitable in this kind of field</p>	<p>F- Swap abstract algebra and Linear algebra; Offer Number Theory earlier; Offer Fil 100 earlier or in first year.</p>
BSED- MATHEMATICS 4	BSED- MATHEMATICS 4
No comments	

Legend: F – Faculty A – Alumni S – Student E – Employer IP – Industry Practitioner

Stakeholders' Involvement in the Evaluation of the School of Education Curriculum at San Isidro College

Matrix 5 shows the comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BSED-Values Education curriculum. A faculty stakeholder commented that VED 107 (*Career Development and work values*) offered in the first semester of the 2nd year should be taken in the 3rd year 1st semester as a career preparation subject. VED 113 (*Values Integration in the various disciplines*) should be taken in the 2nd year during the 1st semester.

Matrix 5. Comments and suggestions of the stakeholders on the BSED-Values Education Curriculum

Comments of the stakeholders on the BSED-VALUES EDUCATION Curriculum	Suggestions of the Stakeholders for the improvement of the BSED- VALUES EDUCATION Curriculum
BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 1	BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 1
F- The subjects offered in the first year are the foundations for the higher years A- The curriculum is well crafted. It certainly meets the standards IP- Theo 101 should be offered in the 1 st semester of the first-year curriculum	IP – Offer Theo 101 in the first semester
BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 2	BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 2
F- VED 107 can be taken in the 3 rd year during the first semester as a career preparation of the students F- The subject for Technology I and II are too far apart that could cause discontinuity of knowledge A- I have concerns on the sequencing of the subjects for the 1 st and 2 nd semesters IP- there are 2 subjects on family life- Theo 102 and VED 106	F- Technology I may be offered during the 2 nd semester A- I suggest that VED 109 (Values Systems) be offered in the first semester; VED 107 in the 3 rd year first semester or VED 111 in the 2 nd year during the 2 nd semester. IP- Theo 102 be replaced by Biblical Theology- Sacred Scriptures and Sacred traditions (Theo 106). Since the Bible is an important foundation of Christian life. Marriage will be discussed in Theo 104 Sacramental Theology
BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 3	BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 3
F- VED 117 can be taken in the 2 nd year 1 st semester F- The Subject Technology I and II are too far apart A- I have a concern on the proper sequencing of Theology subjects specifically Theo 103 and Theo 104 S- Filipino is not connected in the 1 st and 2 nd semester, and also to the field of specialization	F- The subject on Technology II may be offered in the 1 st semester of the 3 rd year A- I suggest to interchange Theo 103 and Theo 104. Theo 103 can be more meaningful if it is offered in the 3 rd year 2 nd semester as it can greatly help in preparing the students for the 4 th year S- GEC 108 (Science) should not be in the 2 nd year, second semester IP- Theo 14 on Sacramental Theology be offered in the 2 nd year during the 2 nd semester. Theo 103 on vocation and mission be offered in the 3 rd year during the 2 nd semester
BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 4	BSED- VALUES EDUCATION 4
No comments	

Legend: F – Faculty A – Alumni S – Student E – Employer IP – Industry Practitioner

Accordingly, Ed 106 which is on *Technology for Teaching and Learning I* should not be too far apart from VED 121 which is *Technology for Teaching and Learning II*. This is offered in the 2nd semester of the 3rd year. The two semester's gap could provide a discontinuing effect for the

students' learning in Technology. Fil 100 offered during the second semester of the 3rd year could be offered earlier so that the students could concentrate in their major field. The stakeholder suggested that VED 109 (*Fil. Values system*) which is offered during the 2nd semester of the 2nd year should be offered in the 2nd year during the 1st semester. VED 119 (Development of Values Education Instructional materials and assessment tools) be offered in the 2nd semester of the 2nd year in preparation for their teaching in the 3rd year.

The industry practitioner stakeholder suggested interchanging Theo 103 and Theo 104 because he finds it more meaningful if this is offered in the 3rd year to prepare the students for the 4th year. He added that VED 102 be swapped with Theo 101 in the first year.

All the comments and suggestions of the different stakeholders were noted for further considerations when the time for curriculum revisions will be done.

Savellano (1999) mentioned that a critical and continuing review and evaluation of the curriculum should focus on content and process and the optimal utilization of the appropriate educational technology and strategies. The impact of training programs on teaching performance and a follow-up on the life and professional career of graduates to assess the success and failure of the programs, could become subjects of research which could provide valuable inputs in curricular revision. The challenge in teacher education is to examine and restructure the curriculum to reflect issues and concerns in our present environment and the megatrends of the 21st century.

Accordingly, Savellano (1999) mentioned that a more effective integration of theory and practice has always been sought in teacher education programs. Such integration requires sound judgment and discernment on the part of teachers. Every effort must be made to understand the school as an organization and the way people behave in it. This requires the early and systematic exposure of prospective teachers to classroom experiences. More and more of such experiences are being carefully woven into the different professional courses as early as the first year. This exposure and even gradual participation would enable prospective teachers to discover whether they really want to teach and intensify their desire to teach. It would enable them to see the relevance or irrelevance in the pre-service program and provide them with a greater understanding of their uniqueness in preparation to teach. The field component of teacher education programs could also provide the bridge between the pre-service and in-service training of teachers.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed that the stakeholders find the SED curriculum to contain subjects that are relevant, well-connected, and could adequately prepare the graduates for their future career as teachers. The involvement of the stakeholders in the evaluation of the curriculum help to improve professional development needs in the area of specialization.

Stakeholders could influence decision making and provide a sense of responsibility; to provide confidence in decision making; to improve the quality of decisions made by the college administration; and to ensure that the curriculum is in line with market needs. Stakeholders' involvement in curriculum evaluation could increase strengthening of the program and chances of the graduate's getting employment. The evaluation shows a need to see the relevance of the subjects in the major field. A program of carefully chosen courses in content is imperative for teachers to develop a solid grasp of the goals and objectives of a field. The curriculum has to be

carefully woven into the different professional courses as early as the first year. This would enable the stakeholders to see the relevance or irrelevance of the subjects and provide them with a greater understanding in their involvement and participation in the evaluation of the curriculum.

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